

Intensifier as Changed from the Impolite Word in Thai

Methawee Yuttapongtada

Abstract—Intensifier is the linguistic term and device that is generally found in different languages in order to enhance and give additional quantity, quality or emotion to the words of each language. In fact, each language in the world has both of the similar and dissimilar intensifying device. More specially, the wide variety of intensifying device is used for Thai language and one of those is usage of the impolite word or the word that used to mean something negative as intensifier. The data collection in this study was done throughout the spoken language style by collecting from intensifiers regarded as impolite words because these words as employed in the other contexts will be held as the rude, swear words or the words with negative meaning. Then, backward study to the past was done in order to consider the historical change. Explanation of the original meaning and the contexts of words use from the past till the present time were done by use of both textual documents and dictionaries available in different periods. It was found that regarding the semantics and pragmatic aspects, subjectification also is the significant motivation that changed the impolite words to intensifiers. At last, it can explain pathway of the semantic change of these very words undoubtedly. Moreover, it is found that use tendency in the impolite word or the word that used to mean something negative will more be increased and this phenomenon is commonly found in many languages in the world and results of this research may support to the belief that human language in the world is universal and the same still reflected that human has the fundamental thought as the same to each other basically.

Keywords—Impolite word, intensifier, Thai, semantic change.

I. INTRODUCTION

SEMANTIC intensification, truly considering, is held as the general phenomenon of language as clearly found in all languages in the world. As an important device, it is the explicit way to help us understand the more clearly meanings and it can be perceivable to the feelings and emotions of message that sender intended to employ in each communication.

Generally, linguists such as [1], [4], [9], have studied about semantic intensification and it can briefly be summarized that intensification is any language way to express the different qualification levels. It can be found the following two aspects; increased and decreased level. Therefore, it is said that semantic intensification can clearly be divided into two types namely; amplification and downtoning. To illustrate such the semantic intensification as specified earlier, the following three example sentences can be brought to consider the semantic intensification;

- a) This novel is good.
- b) This novel is very good.
- c) This novel is fairly good.

In accordance with the three example sentences as mentioned in the above, all the sentences mention about the novel qualifications undoubtedly, but there seems to have the different levels in the intensification degree of meanings. It can obviously be explained that; a) it is just the general affirmative message, b) the speaker or writer used the intensifier 'very' for increasing the meaning of gradable adjective 'good.' In this case, intensifier is called 'amplifier' and c) intensifier 'fairly' weakens the meaning of 'good' and this intensifier is called 'downtoner.'

In this article, only the semantic intensification in the aspect of the increased level or semantic degree (amplifier) will be focused on and taken into account. Hence, the intensifying device to be depicted and explained here will mean the device to increase meaning only.

Many languages in the world, as observed generally, have different types of intensifying devices in increasing the semantic level of word or degree such as phonological device, morphological device; reduplication and modifying device; restricted and unrestricted intensifiers which also have these devices for intensifying in Thai language.

In particularly, Thai language has several words used as the intensifiers. These very Thai words will have the usage or co-appearance with the dissimilar main words [6], [10]. As observed carefully, some words may be employed in order to modify the unrestricted main words. While some words may be used in order to modify the restricted main words. Moreover, there are many impolite words employed as the intensifiers in Thai language. Hence, this article will carry out and explain the reasonable reasons on this language phenomenon. It means these words have some semantic features that are similar to each other. Afterwards, there is the semantic change of impolite words due to the pragmatic context and the mentioned impolite words become intensifier in Thai language.

II. DATA COLLECTION IN THE STUDY

The data used in this study are collected from the spoken language because intensifiers are often employed in order to express feeling or attitude of the speakers or language users. Regarding the current Thai language, it is collected from social media via Internet namely; Facebook, Instagram, Twitter, because the earlier mentioned media are widely used in Thai society; especially it is regarded as the modern media containing many of several contents and their users can express their feelings openly. Sometimes usage of expression done by speakers or language users is better than facing with interlocutor in each speaking or communication. Especially, in

Methawee Yuttapongtada, Ph.D., is with the Faculty of Humanities, Kasetsart University, 50 Ngam Wong Wan Road, Chatuchak, 10900 Bangkok, Thailand (e-mail: methaweey@hotmail.com)

some media such as twitter etc., language users can fully express thought, feeling and attitude that the readers may not know who they are. Furthermore, data in the study is also derived from the general people in Thai society; especially the data from teenagers or university students who usually make the conversation within their group in everyday life.

Data in this study was collected intensifiers used as the impolite words in Thai language. It is said that these words are regarded as rude and swear words or negative words when they are used in other contexts. From the collection of data in this study, many of intensifiers are found as follows;

- โคตร /khô:t/ has literary meaning 'lineage'
- สัตว์ /sàt/ has literary meaning 'animal'
- เหี้ย /hîa/ has literary meaning 'Varanus salvator'
- จิบหาย /chíp-hǎ:y/ has literary meaning 'disaster'
- แม่ /mê:ŋ/ has literary meaning 'your mother'

(This word is derived from the word แม่ /mê:/ 'mother' merged with the word มึง /muŋ/ 'you' (impolite))

Backward study relevant to the past was done in order to consider the meanings of these words and how to use these words in different contexts through the usage of textual documents and dictionaries available in the different periods. By doing so, it will show the change of these words and the important reason or factor that is relevant to cause the semantic change. Not only that, it will also show the pathway of impolite words that are used as the intensifiers in the current Thai language.

III. SEMANTIC CHARACTERISTICS INTENSIFIED IN THAI

Regarding the semantic characteristics of the words as expressed intensification in Thai language [8], [11], [12], the semantic characteristics of words were found as follows;

- 1) Words expressed the high or highest level such as 'สุด' /sùt/ (end); 'สุดๆ' sùt-sùt/ (end); 'ที่สุด' /thî:-sùt/ (end); 'สุดยอด' /sùt-yô:t/ (end of top), for example;
- ทำข่าวแต่ละอย่าง เอาใจเผด็จการสุดๆ

TABLE I
WORD EXPRESSED 'สุดๆ' /sùt-sùt/ (END)

ทำข่าวแต่ละอย่าง เอาใจเผด็จการสุดๆ			
/tham khà:w tè:-la-yà:ŋ	ʔaw-cay	pha-dèt-ka:n	sùt-sùt/
do news each	try to please	dictator	end
Each news is done to absolutely try to please the dictator			

- เด็กคนนี่ฉลาดสุดยอด

TABLE II
WORD EXPRESSED 'สุดยอด' /sùt-yô:t/ (END OF TOP)

เด็กคนนี่ฉลาดสุดยอด			
/dèk khon ni:	cha-là:t	sùt-yô:t/	
child person this	clever	end of top	
This child is the topmost cleaver one			

- 2) Words expressed the numbers and quantity such as 'มาก' /mâ:k/ (much, many); 'นัก' /nák/ (many); and 'แสน' /sǎ:n/ one hundred thousand(etc., for example);
- นี่ถือเป็นเรื่องน่าเศร้าที่สุด

TABLE III
WORD EXPRESSED 'ที่สุด' /thî:-sùt/ (END)

นี่ถือเป็นเรื่องน่าเศร้าที่สุด			
/ní: thî:-	pen rúaŋ	nâ:-sǎw	thî:-sùt/
This	is held as the	saddest	story
This is held as the saddest story			

- ข้าพเจ้าทำได้แม่นยำ

TABLE IV
WORD EXPRESSED 'มาก' /mâ:k/ (MUCH, MANY)

ข้าพเจ้าทำได้แม่นยำ			
/khâ:-pha-cá:w	cam	dá:y mên	mâ:k/
I	remember	got exactly	many
I remember it very exactly			

- โชคดีที่มีสามีแสนดี

TABLE V
WORD EXPRESSED 'แสน' /sǎ:n/ (ONE HUNDRED THOUSAND)

โชคดีที่มีสามีแสนดี					
/thò: chò:k-di: thî: mi:	sǎ:-mi:	sǎ:n	di:/		
You lucky	at have	husband	one hundred		
			thousand	good	
You are lucky to have exactly good husband					

- กับข้าวร้านนี้เขามากกว่าร้านอร่อยนัก

TABLE VI
WORD EXPRESSED 'นัก' /nák/ (MANY)

กับข้าวร้านนี้เขามากกว่าร้านอร่อยนัก			
/khàp-khâ:w-rá:n ní:	khǎw wá: ʔa-ròy	nák/	
dishes shop this	they say	delicious	many
As said, the dishes of this shop is extremely delicious			

- 3) Words expressed the size and weight such as 'หนัก' /nák/ (heavy); 'หนักรหนา' /nák-nǎ:/ (heavy and thick) and 'ใหญ่' /yà:/ (big), for example;

- พอเธอรู้ความจริงก็โกรธใหญ่

TABLE VII
WORD EXPRESSED 'ใหญ่' /yà:/ (BIG)

พอเธอรู้ความจริงก็โกรธใหญ่			
/phò: thò: rú: khwa:m-ciŋ	kó: krò:t	yà:/	
enough she know	truth	also angry	big
Having knew the truth, she got angry greatly			

- เขอกำลังเศร้าหนัก
- เขามีความทุกข์หนักหนา ใครก็ช่วยเขาไม่ได้

Apart from Thai word with intensification or with meaning 'very,' as mentioned in the above, there have also been Pali-

Sanskrit loanwords used in Thai language namely; the word *บรม* /*bo:-rom/* ‘supreme’ and *มหา* /*maha:/* ‘great’ that Thai people used both of them as the intensifiers by putting it in front of the modifiers such as:

- ‘บรมโง่’

TABLE VIII
WORD EXPRESSED ‘หนัก’ / *nàk/* (HEAVY)

เธอกำลังเศร้าหนัก			
/thə:	kam-laj	sāw	nàk/
she	power	regret	heavy
She is regretting severely			

TABLE IX
WORD EXPRESSED ‘หนักหนา’ / *nàk-nā:/* (HEAVY AND THICK)

เขามีความทุกข์หนักหนา ใครก็ช่วยเขาไม่ได้					
/khāw	mi:	khwa:m-thúk	nàk-nā:	khay	kō:
he/she	has	suffering	heavy and thick	who	also
He/she has exceedingly suffered. Nobody cannot help him					

TABLE X
WORD EXPRESSED ‘บรม’ / *bo:-rom/* (SUPREME)

บรมโง่	
/bo:-rom-ma	ngō:/
supreme	stupid
Very stupid	

- ‘มหาโหด’

TABLE XI
WORD EXPRESSED ‘มหา’ / *ma-hā:/* (GREAT)

มหาโหด	
/ma-hā:	hò:t/
great	cruel
Very cruel	

According to the grammatical structure of Pali-Sanskrit and it may also be used ‘โง่บรม’ / *ngō:-bo-rom/* (very stupid); ‘เลวบรม’ / *le:w-bo-rom/* ‘very bad’ in accordance with the grammatical structure of Thai language. For the example words as mentioned, it is seen that the semantic change occurred in Thai language after borrowing Pali-Sanskrit to use with a mixture in Thai language. That is to say that it must be used in good or important meaning in real Pali-Sanskrit, but it is was not used so in Thai language.

4) Words expressed the truth, real such as ‘จริง’ / *ciṅ/* (truly); ‘จริงๆ’ / *ciṅ-ciṅ/* (really); ‘แท้’ / *thé:/* (real) for examples;

- โคนนายคนนี้หลอกยังไม่รู้ตัวอีก ช่างน่าสมเพชแท้

TABLE XII
WORD EXPRESSED ‘แท้’ / *thé:/* (REAL)

โคนนายคนนี้หลอกยังไม่รู้ตัวอีก ช่างน่าสมเพชแท้					
do:n	na:y	khon	ní:	yaṅ	māy rú: tua ?i:k
touch	mister	person	this	yet	no know body again
fool				indeed	sympathize
Don't know that this guy deceived yet. What a pathetic you are!					

- นั่งบ่นแต่เรื่องการเมืองนี่น่า ไร้สาระจริงๆ

TABLE XIII
WORD EXPRESSED ‘จริงๆ’ / *ciṅ-ciṅ/* (REAL-REAL)

นั่งบ่นแต่เรื่องการเมืองนี่น่า ไร้สาระจริงๆ			
/nāṅ	bòn	tè: rúṅaj	ka:n- ráy sǎ:-rá? ciṅ-ciṅ/
sit	mutter	but story	none sense
Muttered only the story on politics. Nonsense really!			

IV. SEMANTIC CHANGE OF INTENSIFIER

According to the semantic characteristics of the intensifier or expression of the meaning ‘very’ in Thai language, it is found that its characteristics is similar to that of many languages in the world and if meanings of these words are considered, it can be showed that these words get the semantic change such as;

หนักหนา		
/nàk-nā:/	→	‘very’
‘heavy and thick’		
จริง		
/ciṅ/	→	‘very’
‘true, real’		
แท้		
/thé:/	→	‘very’
‘real’		

About the semantic change occurred, if the historical matter is considered. It is exactly found that some words were employed with the original or literal meaning and, at the same time it was used as the intensifiers such as *หนักหนา* /*nàk-nā:/* ‘heavy and thick’ etc. As considered from the textual documents in Sukhothai period that Thai people believed that the first writing is done in Thailand, it is found that literal meaning *หนักและหนา* ‘heavy and thick’ is used and expressed as the intensifiers as well.

According to the phenomenon of semantic change as specified in the above, it is said that this phenomenon occurred in many languages. It conformed to the views as depicted undoubtedly by the reference [7] who stated about the grammaticalization that there will be the main word or the word or phrase that are brought to speak restrictedly in society in any context always and the same will be reanalyzed by adding the function of syntax and morpheme. In English, the words of intensifiers met the change in that feature is similar to this case as mentioned earlier such as *verray* (very). Initially, it was the adjective with the meaning ‘true’ for examples;

He was a *verray*, parfit gentil knight.
He was a true, perfect, gentle knight.

However, in the present time the word ‘very’ has become the intensifier already.

The words with meanings ‘true’, ‘real’ in many languages including Thai language are employed as the intensifiers. In this matter of fact, the reference [12] who studied the historical

change of the word จริง /ciŋ/ 'true, real' and แท้ /thé:/ 'real' as became the intensifiers has obviously stated about such the semantic change that it has occurred from the use in pragmatic content by considering the intention of speakers and interpretation of listeners. In other words, it may be dragged to the subjectification as follows;

a) ดิฉันน่ารักเธอแท้ๆ
/di-chăn nà: rák thə: thé:-thé:/
I particle love you real-real
I love you really.

b) ดาราที่เจ็บคอแท้ๆ ป้าป้า
/da:-ra: kô: cèp kho: thé:-thé: pá: pǎ:/
Film star also ache throat real-real aunt father
Film star has a sore throat really, auntie, father.

c) ประหลาดแท้ๆ
/prà-lǎ:t thé:-thé:/
Strange real-real
What a real strange it is!

d) สึกหัดคนของเราให้ผู้อื่นใช้ได้จริงๆ
/fui-k-hát khon khǎng-raw háy chá:y dá:y ciŋ-ciŋ/
Train people our give use get real-real
Train our people to be used really.

e) แลพร้อมเพรียงในการต่อสู้กับศัตรูจริงๆ
/le: phró:m-phriang nay ka:n-tò:-sú: khà:-suik-sàt-tru:
ciŋ-ciŋ/
and all together in fight enemy
real-real

And all together looked in fighting against enemy really.

f) ถ้าเจ้ากระหายจริงๆ จะมาหาเรียนต่อเองบ้างก็คงไม่ขัดข้อง
/thá: cáw kra-hǎ:y ciŋ-ciŋ
If you thirst real-real
cà ma: há: rian tò: aw-:e:ŋ bá:ŋ kô: khon mây
khàt-khǎng/
will come see learn continue oneself else also may
not dissent
If you thirst for it really. Come to continue learning
yourself. I never dissent.

According to the intensification by using the modifiers to express 'reality' or 'truth' as mentioned in the above, it was found that there was usage of the word แท้ /thé:/ 'real' and จริง /ciŋ/ 'true.' The same clearly showed that there may be usage of the word with meaning 'not to lie' or 'true' in order to show the intensification in the reign of King Rama V. These words has raised device of the semantic change. That is to say that the word แท้ /thé:/ 'real' and จริง /ciŋ/ 'true' originally expressed 'not to lie'. The examples in the following sentences are as follows;

ฮึๆ ผลไม้ของข้าพเจ้าแท้ๆ
/hu:~hu:~ phǎn-la-má:y khǎng-khà-pha-cá:w thé:-
thé:/
Chuckle-chuckle fruits mine real-real
Chuckle Chuckle fruits are mine really.

Later, speakers or language users brought these words to employ in the context of sincerity expression or truth repeat in order to intensify the meaning. It can be seen such the words according to the following sentence;

ดิฉันน่ารักเธอแท้ๆ
/di-chăn nà: rák thə: thé:-thé:/
I particle love you real-real
I love you really.

According to the above-mentioned example sentences, the word แท้ /thé:/ 'real' is expressed by the speakers or language users who do not lie in order to show their sincerity. At the same time, there have also been the occurred meaning 'very' that is regarded as the intensification as well. Accordingly, such the sentences have two meanings namely; love you really (do not lie) and love you very much (express the intensification). The example in item b) is the same to the example in item a) However, as considered generally about the example of sentence in item c) saying ประหลาดแท้ๆ (what a real strange it is!), its meaning on 'true story' and 'not to lie' becomes decreased, but the newer meaning 'very' is increased and the same is regarded as the intensifiers.

The word จริง /ciŋ/ 'true, real' used as the intensifiers undoubtedly appeared in the reign of King Rama V also has the semantic change which is similar to the word แท้ /thé:/ 'real' as explained in the above already.

According to the word จริง /ciŋ/ 'true, real' and แท้ /thé:/ 'real' as specified in the above, both of them still be used in the current Thai language, but the word จริง /ciŋ/ 'true, real' will become more popular word than the word แท้ /thé:/ 'real' in use for making the intensification in Thai society.

V. IMPOLITE WORD USED AS INTENSIFIER IN THAI

At the present time, there are many words of Thai language that has expressed the meaning 'very' or intensifier, because the speakers or language users feel that such the word is not able to communicate the meaning as they wished. For an example; the speakers or language users would like to say that 'lady is very beautiful.' In this context, the language use of 'very beautiful' is not enough to express their inner feeling [12]. To support the matter of fact as mentioned earlier, once Thai people have spoken the following sentence by using the intensifier;

ผู้หญิงคนนี้สวยระเบิดเลย
/phú:-yǎŋ khon ní: sǔay ra-bè:t lə:y/
lady person this beautiful bomb pass
This lady is very beautiful.

Here, the word 'ระเบิด' /ra-bè:t/ is verb meaning 'burst, blast.' The speakers or language users brought this very word to employ in order to express the meaning 'very' by raising the semantic feature that communicate 'violence' of the word 'bomb' in order to express the meaning 'very.' By doing so, it can respond and it is enough to their wish in feeling expression

of the speakers or language users instead of the word มาก /mâ:k/ 'very.'

Furthermore, to illustrate the phenomenon of impolite words used as the intensifiers in Thai language, it can be observed that at the present time, some speakers or language users in Thai society said the following intensifiers;

ผู้หญิงคนนี้สวยโคตร/โคตรสวย
/phû:-yîŋ khon ní: sŭay khô:t/
Lady person this beautiful lineage
/phû:-yîŋ khon ní: khô:t sŭay/
Lady person this lineage beautiful
This lady is very beautiful.
ผู้หญิงคนนี้สวยฉิบหาย
/phû:-yîŋ khon ní: sŭay chíp-hă:y/
Lady person this beautiful disaster
This lady is extremely beautiful.
ผู้หญิงคนนี้สวยสัตว์
/phû:-yîŋ khon ní: sŭay sàt/
Lady person this beautiful animal
This lady is absolutely beautiful.
ผู้หญิงคนนี้สวยเหี้ยๆ
/phû:-yîŋ khon ní: sŭay hîa-hîa/
Lady person this beautiful vanarus salvator-
vanarus salvator
This lady is exceedingly beautiful.

To choose the word 'ระเบิด' /ra-bò:t/; 'โคตร' /khô:t/; 'ฉิบหาย' /chíp-hă:y/ สัตว์ /sàt/ and 'เหี้ย' /hîa/ in order use in Thai language for expressing the meaning 'very' as mentioned in the above, it caused the semantic change and uses.

For the expression of meaning 'very' that was employed by those the speakers or language users in the above, it is regarded as the language phenomenon that is reasonable in explanation according to the example words as illustrated above;

According to the word 'โคตร' /khô:t/ 'lineage'; and 'ฉิบหาย' /chíp-hă:y/ 'disaster' as mentioned in the above, it can be analyzed clearly that the speakers or language users choose these words because they have the semantic characteristics with intensity. However, such the word 'โคตร' /khô:t/ and 'ฉิบหาย' /chíp-hă:y/ are available in the Dictionary of Siamese Language [2]. In such the Dictionary of Siamese as the first dictionary of Thailand, meanings of the word 'โคตร' /khô:t/ and 'ฉิบหาย' /chíp-hă:y/ are as follows;

'โคตร' /khô:t/ is the name of lineage of grandfather and grandmother of those people who was born from generation to generation of family.

The use of word 'ฉิบหาย' /chíp-hă:y/ can be traced to the Sukhothai period of Thailand. The Wat Sri Chum (วัดศรีชุม) inscription, composed around the 14th century, included the phrase บิหฉิบหาย or in modern spelling บิหฉิบหาย /bò:-hây-chíp-hă:y/. 'ฉิบ' /chíp/ and 'หาย' /hă:y/ are actually synonyms, meaning to disappear or come to ruin. They appeared in a 1361 inscription in a similar context; บิหฉิบหาย (Modern: บิหฉิบหาย /hây-thùŋ-thí:-chíp-thí:-hă:y/)

After that, the Dictionary of Siamese gives the following definition;

'ฉิบหาย' /chíp-hă:y/ is the name of disasters. For example; for those people who were rich become poor people after experiencing disaster.

It can clearly be observed that at the beginning, the literal meaning of the word 'โคตร' /khô:t/ and 'ฉิบหาย' /chíp-hă:y/ does not mean the negative thing at all. Later, the two words are brought to employ in order to express the negative meaning. That is to say that for those people who did very bad deed will be abused and cursed about their lineage. In this, it makes the word 'โคตร' /khô:t/ 'lineage' become the word with negative meaning because of their usage in the pragmatic context. For the word 'ฉิบหาย' /chíp-hă:y/ 'disappear' or 'ruin' are used in the pragmatic context by cursing that caused the great ruins. From such the meaning of disappearing, there have been the pejorative meaning occurred afterwards. As the pragmatic context occurred, it makes the two words become the word that gradually diverted to negative meanings more and more until there have been the expressive meaning that is held as the abuse and curse words occurred in the high degree. Later, the speakers or language users brought the two words in order to express their meaning 'very' instead of original meaning. Initially, they put it together with the main word with meaning 'negative, very bad' such as;

'เลวโคตร'
/le:w khô:t/
bad lineage
Very bad
'โคตรเลว'
/khô:t le:w/
lineage bad
Very bad
'เลวฉิบหาย'
/le:w chíp-hă:y/
bad disaster
Very bad

However, the speakers or language users brought the two words in order to express the negative meaning later, but their meaning seems to be the less bad meaning or they are used for communicating the meaning along with the attitude of the speakers or language users. Mostly, their meaning is used in the negative way such as;

'โง่โคตร'
/ŋô: khô:t/
silly lineage
Very silly
'โคตรโง่'
/khô:t ŋô:/
lineage silly
Very silly
'โง่ฉิบหาย'
/yîŋ chíp-hă:y/

arrogant disaster
Very arrogant
'เมื่อโคตร'
/bùa khô:t/
bored lineage
Very bored
'แข็งลิบหาย'
/seŋ chip-hă:y/
Sick disaster
Very sick
'ร้อนโคตร'
/rô:n khô:t/
hot lineage
Very hot
'เผ็ดลิบหาย'
/pèt chip-hă:y/
spicy disaster
Very spicy

Afterwards, some speakers or language users; especially teenagers brought the word โคตร /khô:t/ and ลิบหาย /chip-hă:y/ to use and put them with the words with the positive meaning, for examples;

'คนอะไรเก่งลิบหาย'
/khon ʔa-ray kèŋ chip-hă:y/
person what excellent disaster
What a very excellent he/she is!
'กาแฟร้านนี้อร่อยโคตร'
/ka:-fe: rá:n ní: ʔa-ròy khô:t/
coffee shop this delicious lineage
This coffee shop is very delicious.
'น้องคนนี่ร้องเพลงเพราะโคตร'
/nóng khon ní: rỏ:ŋ phreŋ phrỏ? khô:t/
younger persn this sing song melodious lineage
This younger person sings a very melodious song
'น้องคนนี่ร้องเพลงเพราะลิบหาย'
/nóng khon ní: rỏ:ŋ phreŋ phrỏ? chip-hă:y/
younger person this sing song melodious disaster
This younger person sings a very melodious song.

In the case of the word 'สัตว์' /sàt/ 'animal' and 'เหี้ย' /hía/ 'Varanus salvator' that used for expressing the meaning 'very' it, as same as the word 'โคตร' /khô:t/ and 'เหี้ย' /hía/ also has the reasons in use. Firstly, the two words were brought to use as the abuse for those people who have bad and wicked behavior. Here, it can be compared with the action of animals, while the word 'เหี้ย' /hía/ is regarded as the unlucky from the belief in the old time. Explanation about this can be found as follows;

'เหี้ย' /hía/ is the quadruped and its body is long like crocodile. It lives in both water and land [2].

'เหี้ยขึ้นเรือน' /hía-khuon-ruan/ means the Varanus salvator climbed up the house and Thai people generally believed that it is unlucky and the time of property loss will reach the owner of house [2].

The speakers or language users employed the word 'สัตว์' /sàt/

and 'เหี้ย' /hía/ as the abuse in impolite and extreme degree. Later, they brought both of them to modify the main words in order to express the bad meaning, attitude or feeling to each thing, for examples;

'เลวเหี้ย'
/le:w hía/
bad Varanus salvator
Very bad
'เลวสัตว์'
/le:w sàt/
bad animal
Very bad
'เผ็ดเหี้ยๆ'
/phèt hía-hía/
spicy Varanus salvator- Varanus salvator
Very spicy
'เผ็ดสัตว์'
/phèt sàt/
spicy animal
Very spicy
'ยากเหี้ยๆ'
/yâ:k hía-hía/
difficult Varanus salvator- Varanus salvator
Very difficult
'ยากสัตว์'
/yâ:k sàt/
difficulty animal
Very difficult

Then, the two words are brought to express the meaning 'very' by putting together with main word having the positive meaning such as;

'เก่งเหี้ย'
/kèŋ hía/
Excellent Varanus salvator
Very excellent
'สวยสัตว์'
/sủay sàt/
Beautiful animal
Very beautiful
'อร่อยเหี้ยๆ'
/ʔa-rỏy hía-hía/
Tasty Varanus salvator- Varanus salvator
Very tasty

However, it is said that the semantic change of the word expressed the meaning as depicted in the above will depend upon the significant factors namely; situation, age, gender of the speakers or language users. As observed, the word with meaning 'very' will be used in the informal situation. Especially, the speakers and listeners will be the close persons and often it is used for the teenagers and in the male gender more than female.

According to the light as mentioned in the above, it can be said that the semantic change from the impolite words to

intensifiers will occur in due time and the process of the semantic change can be explained about the cause factor concerned clearly. Throughout the historical language study, the semantic change can be found clearly.

The impolite words which become the intensifiers used in Thai language have lots of numbers and such the words was not impolite from the beginning. Later, these words are brought to abuse, curse, and swear words. Then, these words are brought to employ in the negative way and modify the words for the

general meaning. Lastly, they are brought to use as the modifiers or intensifiers of those words which have the positive meaning. As observed the process of the semantic change, it will be interpreted from the use context that is the factor of pragmatics including the important factor of feeling of the speakers or language users concerned. To understand the semantic change occurred, it can show the pathway of semantic change as follows;

- (1) original meaning→ (none-expressive) (+negative sense) (+ degree)
(2) abuse, swear and curse words→ (+negative sense) (+expressive) (+ degree)
(3) intensifier used with negative word (+expressive)
→(4) intensifier used with neutral meaning word (+expressive) (+ degree) →(5) intensifier used with positive meaning word (+expressive) (+ degree)

According to pathway of semantic change of the impolite words to become the intensifiers in Thai language, it is seen that the speakers or languages users brought some senses of the original meaning in order to use in pejorative context; abuse, swear and curse words. Later, they are brought to use as the intensifiers of the main word which consists of the negative meaning having pejorative connotation and emphatic sense. Afterwards, the impolite words are brought to use as the intensifiers of main word consisting of the neutral meaning and used as the modifier that consists of the positive meaning later. In this context, the pejorative sense has disappeared due to the linguistic and pragmatic context, especially tone of voice and facial expression can remove all pejorative sense. Interpretation in this context has occurred from subjectification in interpretation of the speakers and listeners [3].

VI. IMPOLITE WORD BECOMES INTENSIFIER IN THE WORLD'S LANGUAGES

As considered generally, the phenomenon of those impolite words which become the intensifier are found not only in Thai language, but also in other languages which are available in the world, because the speakers of those language want to emphasize more meanings and add more degrees of feeling to whatever they have mentioned in communication. On this matter, it can see an example of intensifier word use from English people who employ the word 'fuck' as the intensifier instead of other intensifiers in their communication.

In accordance with the light as mentioned in the above, it can undoubtedly be explained that an intensifier such as so deflates the low value of the item to which it refers yet further. Taboo intensifier also performs this function by virtue of the fact that they fill the intensifier slot s for example fucking lazy (=extremely lazy) (also note: fuck all (=nothing at all), and what the fuck (=what on earth)). However, an intensifier such as fuck not only performs this deflationary function, but also intensifiers the emotional experience for the perceiver (cf. Jay 1992: 11) A taboo intensifier itself can violate the social norms of particular groups about appropriate language. Such intensifiers, then, are an effective way of increasing the intensification of conventional impoliteness expressions [5].

Not only that, there are other examples of impolite word use in order to intensify and add degrees of feeling of the speakers or language users derived from different languages in the world, they are as follows;

In French, the word 'putain' means prostitute and it is brought to use in the following sentence; c' est putain bon 'it is very delicious.'

About the word 'putain', its direct meaning goes to prostitute that French people use it as Slang in the feature of interjection or swear word rather rude word. The same, as considered generally, may be compared with the word 'fucking' as employed for communication in English.

In Chinese, the words '他' /tā/ (he/she) + '妈' /mā/ (mother) + '的' /de/ (Thing) = 他妈的美 /tā mā de měi/ are brought to use in the sentence meaning 'very beautiful.' Such the sentence seems to be similar to Khmer because Khmer people employed this word in their language in communication as well. 'គួរ' /chaŋaŋ/ (delicious) + 'កូ' /coy/ (fucking) + 'ម្តាយ' /mra:y/ (mother) 'very delicious.'

According to the light as mentioned in the above, it can explicitly be observed that the word with the impolite meaning or rude words derived from 婊 + 屄 /mê:/ + /muŋ/ in Thai language, Chinese and Khmer are also brought to use as the intensifiers in the same way, although the abuse is regarded as the very impolite in Asian culture.

VII. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

To sum up, throughout study of the intensifiers of the words group which is derived from impolite or rude words in Thai language, it can obviously be explained the process of the semantic change including pragmatics through the thorough historical change of language. Furthermore, the pathway of the earlier mentioned change occurred in this very Thai language is similar to that of change of impolite words to intensifiers of other languages available in the world as well.

Moreover, as studied the intensifiers as changed from the impolite words in Thai language, it was found that these words, truly speaking, are used as the interjection or swear and curse

words in speaking as well. In particularly, such the phenomenon has also occurred in any language.

Through doing so, it can be believed that human language in the world is universal and the same still reflected that human has the fundamental thought as the same to each other basically. For the next study, if there will be the study of intensifiers derived from different languages in the world, the significant issue in order to view and understand the holistic view and thought through the thorough use of human language as language universal should be done and taken into account.

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